

Synthesis, characterization, luminescent properties and biological activity studies of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with sulphur and some nitrogen donors

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Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} ion with 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate {CED²⁻ = [S₂C=C(COOC₂H₅)(CN)]²⁻} and heterocyclic nitrogen bases such as pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic) have been isolated and characterized by analytical data and physico-chemical techniques such as molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and fluorescence spectral studies. The complexes do not decompose up to 300 °C and are only soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance data of complexes in DMF solution show its non electrolytic nature. The magnetic moment values of the complexes indicate paramagnetic character corresponding to two unpaired electrons. Distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes have been proposed on magnetic and electronic spectral studies. Infrared spectral studies suggest bidentate chelating behaviour of CED²⁻ ion and unidentate behavior of nitrogen donors in these complexes.

Fluorescence study of the complexes show the binding of ligand to metal. These complexes also show antibacterial and antifungal activity *in vitro*.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, nickel(II), 1,1-dithiolates, luminescent properties, antibacterial and antifungal.

Introduction

A variety of dithiolate ligands have been used to synthesize transition as well as non-transition metal complexes to study their coordination behavior. Thus the coordination chemistry of metal dithiolate has been an area of interest for several years^{1,2}. The interest in this area stems from various reasons such as optical recording materials³, radio-protective activities⁴, anti-tumor activity³, stabilization of transition metal ions in its higher oxidation states^{5,6,14-16}, facile redox behavior¹⁷, stabilization of square planar geometry around transition metal ions^{18,19}, interesting spectral and magnetic properties⁴⁻¹⁶, electron transfer reactions and electrically conducting materials⁷⁻¹¹ along with industrial and biological applications^{2,3}.

Among 1,1-dithioligands, 1-cyano-1-carboethoxy-

ethylene-2,2-dithiolate (CED²⁻) shows exciting coordination properties by virtue of its chelating and bridging behaviour which have been found in its binary, ternary and heterobimetallic complexes^{1,2,12-16}.

The literature survey reveals that there is no report on mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} ion involving 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate and heterocyclic tertiary monoamines.

In view of the above, we undertake the synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} ion with 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate (CED²⁻) and some heterocyclic nitrogen donors such as pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic), β -picoline (β -pic) or γ -picoline (γ -pic). The results of our investigations are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used in this study, obtained from E. Merck, were of GR grade or equivalent quality, α -, β - and γ -picolines were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company. The complexes, $\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$, $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$, $\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$ and the ligand $\text{K}_2\text{CED}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared by known literature procedure^{14,20}.

Synthesis of complexes :

Synthesis of $\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (1) :

$\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$ (0.80 g, 2 mmol) was dissolved in 25 cm³ of pyridine slowly with vigorous stirring which resulted a blackish yellow solution. The solution was filtered and filtrate was allowed to evaporate naturally. After one month a sticky black product was obtained which was washed with ether several times resulting a teak brown powder. Finally, it was suction filtered and air-dried; UV-Vis bands (nm) : 917, 816, 708, 600, 520, 465 in solid state at RT; 916, 614, 580, 467 in DMF solution; Fluorescence emission band (nm) : 473 in solid state at RT with excitation at 365 nm.

Synthesis of $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (2) :

The complex (2) was synthesized similar to the complex (1) with starting materials $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$; UV-Vis bands (nm) : 926, 815, 710, 589, 518, 465 in solid state at RT; 920, 603, 539, 446 in DMF solution; Fluorescence emission band (nm) : 474 in solid state at RT with excitation at 365 nm.

Synthesis of $\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (3) :

The complex (3) was synthesized similar to the complex (1) with starting materials $\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{CED})$; UV-Vis bands (nm) : 926, 870, 709, 584, 518, 465 in solid state at RT; 917, 604, 535, 476 in DMF solution; Fluorescence emission band (nm) : 473 in solid state at RT with

excitation at 365 nm.

Analysis of the complexes :

The complexes were analyzed for nickel and sulphur using standard literature procedures²¹. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined micro-analytically on CE 440 Exeter, USA.

Physical measurements :

The molar conductance of the complexes in DMF solution were measured using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 304. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature on a Cahn-Faraday electro balance using $[\text{CoHg}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Experimental magnetic susceptibility values have been corrected for diamagnetism by the procedures given by Figgis and Lewis²² and Earnshaw²³. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol (4000–200 cm⁻¹) and in KBr pellets (4000–400 cm⁻¹) on a Bomem DA-8 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The electronic and fluorescence spectra of the complexes in the solid state were recorded on a Foster-Freeman Video Spectral Comparator-5000 while electronic spectra in DMF solution were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model Lamda-25 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Analytical data together with colour, yield, magnetic moment and molar conductance values are presented in Table 1. Important infrared spectral data and biological activities data are listed in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Results and discussion

The analytical data and stoichiometries of the complexes reveal the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the composition, $\text{NiL}_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ [L = α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic; CED^{2-} = 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate]. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The complexes do not decom-

Table 1. Analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic moments of Ni^{II} complexes

Complex (Colour)	% Yield (Dec. temp. °C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (DMF))	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Ni	S	N	C	H		
$\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (1) (Teak brown)	80 (> 300)	9.67 (9.94)	10.41 (10.86)	11.65 (11.86)	56.34 (56.96)	4.40 (4.95)	58.0	2.85
$\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (2) (Teak brown)	70 (> 300)	9.30 (9.94)	10.22 (10.86)	11.30 (11.86)	56.45 (56.96)	4.70 (4.95)	56.0	2.77
$\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$ (3) (Dark brown)	65 (> 300)	9.40 (9.94)	10.32 (10.86)	11.44 (11.86)	56.50 (56.96)	4.62 (4.95)	54.0	2.87

Table 2. Characteristic IR bands (cm^{-1}) for the Ni^{II} mixed ligand complexes

Complexes	$\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(=\text{CS}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$
1	2203vs	1638s	1369vs, 1400s	1027vs, 925s	847w	410w	320w
2	2205s	1640s	1371m, 1402m	1027s, 918m	832w	420w	300w
3	2202s	1638s	1368m, 1400m	1026s, 918m	810w	405w	310w

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

Table 3. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of ligand and Ni^{II} complexes

Complexes	Antibacterial activity			Antifungal activity	
	Zone of inhibition (mm)			Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
$\text{K}_2\text{CED.H}_2\text{O}$ (L)	25	24	26	-	20
$\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$	24	23	25	-	21
$\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$	25	24	27	-	20
$\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$	26	23	26	-	21
Streptomycin (S)	28	25	28	24	-
Fluconazole (S)	-	-	-	-	22

S = Standard drug, L = Ligand.

pose up to 300 °C. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF solutions indicate non-electrolytic nature of complexes²⁴.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moment values of complexes (1-3) lie in the range 2.77-2.87 B.M. suggesting paramagnetism corresponding to two unpaired electrons. The solid state electronic spectra show three absorption bands in the regions 10800-12270, 14084-19305 and 21505 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) respectively suggesting octahedral coordination around Ni^{II} in these complexes. The ν_1 and ν_2 bands show definite splitting suggesting distortion of octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} in these complexes. The splitting of ν_2 bands are observed in the regions 14084-14124 and 16667-19305 cm^{-1} in the spectra of these complexes which may arise due to spin-orbit coupling that mixes the ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and 1E_g states, which are very close in energy at the Δ_0 value given by the ligands present in these mixed ligand complexes²⁵. The electronic spectra of the complexes in DMF solution also show three absorption bands in the ranges 10917-10869 (ν_1), 16583-18691 (ν_2) and 21008-22421 cm^{-1} (ν_3). The definite splitting of ν_2 bands in three complexes suggest distortion in octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes.

IR spectra of ligand and complexes :

The infrared spectra of the mixed ligand complexes

have been interpreted in the light of earlier investigations^{1,20,26-28} on transition and non-transition metal dithiolates. The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes display characteristic stretching frequencies associated with $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$, $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{CS}_2$, C-S and M-S from CED^{2-} and aryl ring vibrations with metal heterocyclic nitrogen vibrations from py, α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic.

The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ band, appearing at 2190 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_2\text{CED.H}_2\text{O}$, is observed with positive shifts in the range 2202-2205 cm^{-1} in its mixed ligand complexes suggesting non-involvement of a nitrile group of the ligand in bonding. The existence of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band in the region 1638-1640 cm^{-1} in these mixed ligand complexes are in the same region as observed for $\text{K}_2\text{CED.H}_2\text{O}$ suggesting the non-involvement of carbonyl oxygen in bonding. The complexes exhibit three strong to very strong bands in the region 1368-1402, 1026-1027 and 918-925 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_1[\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})]$, $\nu_2[\nu_{\text{as}}(=\text{CS}_2)]$ and $\nu_3[\nu_{\text{s}}(=\text{CS}_2)]$ vibrations respectively of C= CS_2 structure which were found in $\text{K}_2\text{CED.H}_2\text{O}$ at 1320, 1020 and 930 cm^{-1} respectively^{12,20}. In some complexes $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ appear as splitted (doublet or triplet) indicating lowering of its symmetry. The positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ bands suggest that dinegative chelating form of ligand, 1-cyano-1-carboethoxyethylene-2,2-dithiolate, is dominant in these complexes. The occurrence of a single weak to strong band in the region 810-847 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in these

complexes indicates symmetrical bonding of both the sulphur atoms of the ligand to the metal ion²⁶.

The mixed ligand complexes containing heterocyclic nitrogen donors show in-plane ring and out-of-plane ring deformation bands in the ranges 611–665 and 405–420 cm^{-1} respectively indicating coordination through nitrogen atom as these bands have found positive shifts with respect to its corresponding bands in its free form. The $\nu(\text{C-H})$ (aromatic ring) arising from aromatic ligands in these complexes is observed as weak band(s) in the region 3000–3100 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{C-H})$ (aliphatic) for complexes containing α -pic, β -pic, γ -pic and/or CED²⁻ is observed as weak intensity bands in the region 2930–2980 cm^{-1} suggesting their presence in the mixed ligand complexes.

The non-ligand bands observed in the ranges 405–420 and 300–320 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of mixed ligand complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ ²⁷ and $\nu(\text{M-S})$ ²⁸ modes respectively.

Luminescent properties :

The complexes (1), (2) and (3) show fluorescence emission bands at 473, 474 and 473 nm respectively in solid state at RT when they are excited at 365 nm (Fig. 2)

which are very close to emission band at 476 nm observed for free ligand, $\text{K}_2\text{CED} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, under similar condition. This indicates that intra ligand excitation is responsible for this emission of complexes. It is clear that blue-shift of emission occurs, which is probably due to the coordination of ligands, because photoluminescence behaviour is closely associated with the local environment²⁹.

$\text{NiL}_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$; L = α -pic, β -pic or γ -pic
 Fig. 1. Proposed structure of the Ni^{II} complexes.

Fig. 2. Emission spectrum of the ligand and Ni^{II} complexes : (a) $\text{K}_2\text{CED} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (b) $\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$, (c) $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$, (d) $\text{Ni}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{py})_2(\text{CED})$.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity studies :

The synthesized complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against Gram-positive (*B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* etc.) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* etc.) microorganism by disc diffusion method and were compared with the standard drug Streptomycin. The complexes showed better antibacterial activity on the basis of their M.I.C. values than their corresponding ligand ($K_2CED.H_2O$) and standard drug one. The synthesized complexes were also screened for their antifungal activity *in vitro* against fungi *Candida albicans* by microplate method of Eloff, using broth nutrient as the medium and were compared with the standard drug Fluconazole. The complexes also showed better antifungal activity on the basis of their M.I.C. values than their corresponding ligand ($K_2CED.H_2O$) and standard drug one³⁰.

Conclusions :

The distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II} ion in these complexes have been proposed based on analytical data, magnetic susceptibility and spectral studies. The infrared spectral studies suggest bidentate chelating behaviour of CED^{2-} and unidentate bonding mode of heterocyclic nitrogen bases in these complexes. These complexes show blue-shift emission at room temperature with respect to ligand at 365 nm excitation wavelength. These complexes show antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive (*B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) microorganism. These complexes also show antifungal activity against fungi *Candida albicans*. The proposed structure of the complexes is shown in Fig. 1.

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